

Field reaction of released and prereleased rice varieties to sheath blight and leaf scald diseases

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Sheath blight and leaf scald diseases of rice have been gaining importance in this locality since they were first reported

Reaction of rices to sheath blight and leaf scald in West Bengal, India.

Variety or line	Reaction to	
	Sheath blight	Leaf scald
TN1	S	S
Bala	S	S
Ratna	MR	R
Padma	MR	MR
Karuna	S	S
IR8	S	S
IR20	S	MR
IR22	S	S
IR24	S	S
Jaya	S	S
IR26	MR	S
Vijaya	HS	S
Pankaj	MR	S
Jayanti	S	S
Sona	S	S
Mashuri	R	S
ADT-27	S	MR
Jagannath	S	MR
Palman-579	S	S
IET-849	MR	MR
Kumar	S	MR
Rajeswari	MR	MR
Hema	MR	S
Pusa-2-21	S	S
IR28	S	S
IR30	S	MR
IET-2914 (RP-79-14)	S	MR
Kalinga-I	MR	S
Improved Sabarmati	S	S
CR 44-35	MR	MR
CR 44-117-1	MR	S
CR 44-1 18-1	S	S
CR 44-1 19-1	HS	S
CR 44-1	S	MR
CR 110-174	HS	S
CR 115-94	MR	MR
CR 36-148	S	MR
CR 126-42-1	S	S
IR442-2-58	S	MR
IET 3233	S	MR
IET 3266	S	S
RP 633-680-1-1-1-1	MR	S
IET 2508	MR	MR
RP 4-14	R	MR

R = resistant; MR = moderately resistant; S = susceptible; HS = highly susceptible.

from this laboratory about 8 years ago. Observations on the field reactions of some released and prereleased varieties to these diseases are presented in the table.

Widespread Occurrence of leaf scald and ufra diseases of rice in Assam, India

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The diseases leaf scald (cause: *Rhynchosporium oryzae*) and ufra (cause: *Ditylenchus angustus*) occurred widely under natural conditions in the

Rice varieties and lines infected with leaf scald. Assam Agricultural University, Jorhat, India.

Leaf scald infection		
Severe		
BR 150-2B-5	IET 5 11 3 (RP 872-20-4-7-2)	B 2350-7-3-3-1
BR 167-2B-1	IET 5447 (R 27-25 11)	B 2360-6-7-1-2
BR 167-2B-3	IET 5487 (RJR 115-2681)	153/54
IET 2877 (BK 284)	IET 5518 (R 35-2740)	DJ 684D
IET 3877 (TNAU 13610)	IET 5552 (R 155-73-320)	A 6-1 0-37
IET 4823 (OR 63-242)	IET 5554 (RJR 113-251)	IR3464-217-3
IET 4835 (OR 1102)	CR 141-4000-2-192	
Trace		
BR 166-2B-13	Amol 1-82	IR4427-51-6-3
BR 169-1-1	Macuspana A75	IR4427-119-6-1
Sein Talay	62-335	IR4427-253-5-2
IET 5105 (RP 572-68-1-1-1)	74-5461	IR4427-279-4-2
B 539b-KPJ-3-5-3-2	Kaohsiung-sen-yu 104	IR4608-6-2
B 541b-Pn-7-1-2-3	Kaohsiung-yu 974	IR46 13-54-5
B 542b-Pn-19-4-1-1	RD 7 (SPR 6726-134-2-26)	IR4625-90-2
B 599d-Pn-139-1-2	IR2307-117-2-1-2	IR4625-90-3
B 805d-Mr-16-8-3	IR2307-486-5-3	1R4707-207-3
B 1014b-Pn-1-3-1	IR2793-80-2-2	IR4816-70-1
B 1014b-Pn-18-1-4	IR2798-143-3-2	IR5257-77-1
B 1293b-Pn.24-2-1	IR2823-103-5-1	BR 4
B 1742b-Pn-22-1-2	IR4227-180-3-2	B 541b-Kn-58-5-3
B 1991-Pn-43-4-1	IR4227-289-1-3	IR2058-78-1-3-2-3
B 2360-2-9-3-4	IR4228-7-1-3	Code #14013
B 2360-6-9-5	IR4215-4-3-1	IR5491-4-8
B 2932-2-3-2-5-3	IR4422-51-1-1	IET 3331
Si2	IR4427-23-2-3	KLG 6987-133-2
Vijaya (Sel.)		

Invitation to authors

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